

METHODOLOGICAL FUNCTIONS OF THE WORDS DENOTING SIGNS
IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES IN THE ANALYSIS OF
THE LITERARY TEXT

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to revealing the important functions of adjectives denoting a sign in English and Uzbek languages. In addition, the linguistic characteristics of adjectives in both languages were comparatively analyzed

Key words: *national-cultural character, language formation, Symbolic words, Denotative words, explanatory dictionaries, figuratively serve, Linguistic-cultural analysis, linguistic landscape.*

In world linguistics, the scope of research devoted to the analysis of the expression of cultural signs in language, the understanding of the world based on concepts, and the mental approach to naming reality is expanding. During its historical development, the language reflects the social process and changes. Studying the linguistic landscape of the world, elucidating the living area, lifestyle, mental characteristics and national-cultural character of the peoples, provides an opportunity to thoroughly analyze the principles of ethno-cultural ethics, social relations, forms of communication between nations, moral and cultural standards of behavior. Analyzing the relationship between language and culture, reflecting the national-cultural characteristics of language units, determining the level of expression of national values and traditions is one of the urgent issues of today's global development, where cultures are coming into contact.

Symbolic concepts are related to the process of language formation. When a person expresses the landscape of the world in his language, he first pays attention to the signs of things - appearance, color, aggregate state, shape. Therefore, the concepts related to signs are also reflected in the naming of things and objects. For example, if the naming of "tomato" is based on the sign of "yellowness" (tomato-tomato is a word meaning "golden apple" in Italian; the initial appearance of the tomato was yellow), the semantics of the lexeme "driver" initially The "fire-lighting" feature was taken into account (chauffeur-chauffeur means "fire-lighter" in French).

Symbolic words are described in different ways in scientific literature. The sign is used in a narrow sense for words belonging to the category of adjectives. In the Uzbek language, there is no special morphological indicator that expresses the meaning of sign - quality. The use of some words both as nouns and adjectives is determined by this. Linguist N.F. Katanov did not distinguish between noun and adjective. He worked on the features of the Kazakh-Kyrgyz and Turkic-Tatar languages. In both English and Uzbek languages the adjective qualifies or modifies a substance: English Uzbek a red apple qizil olma a clever student aqlli talaba a new building yangi bino red pepper qizil qalampir.

In English and Uzbek the adjective usually forms combinations with:

1. nouns: Eng.: an interesting book, a tall tree, a strong man etc. Uzb.: qiziqarli kitob, baland daraxt etc.
2. link-verbs: Eng.: was strong, was clever, was old Uzb.: kuchli edi, aqlli edi, qari edi
3. adverbs: Eng.: very interesting, very old Uzb.: juda qiziqarli, juda eski In English the adjective can combine with the so-called prop word "one" (the red one, the yellow one).

In the languages compared the typical functions of the adjective are those of attribute and predicate: The adjective as an attribute: Eng.: I have brought him an interesting book. Uzb.: Men unga qiziqarli kitob olib keldim.

Morphological unit plays an essential role to learn e.g. reading texts easily, gives vocabulary knowledge to identify words and recognize their meanings while they engage with the learning word or reading one[2]. The adjective - a grammatical part of speech modifies and describes a noun. Furthermore, it tells some descriptive ideas of the noun and they are: size, color, shape, origin, state, character and etc. Because of the differences of geographic environment of the two nations, the grammatical structures of the part of speech – there are some differences in forming the words of adjectives, adding the prefixes and suffixes, forming of comparison degrees and etc. Some adjectives may have more one field, so it is difficult to define the made words from the root ones. The distinctive feature of Uzbek language word formation way is composition which can not be found in other compared languages. Finally, from the analysis of compared languages can be found several similarities, it is possible to show the existence of types of affixation in both languages, or amount of derived words or suffixes, which can change the meaning from one part of speech into another.

Denotative words mainly belong to the category of adjectives. The fact that the word in the noun family has both a denotative and a connotative meaning is a characteristic of the nature of Turkic languages, which ensures a high level of expressiveness. Statistics of lexemes denoting signs in the Uzbek language are presented in the research. In particular, R. Inoyatova, based on the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", determined that there are 550 words denoting the state of a person, 780 adjectives denoting the state of an object, and 420 adjectives denoting signs of various events. Z. Mamarajabova mentions that 20% (540) of the 1,000 descriptive adjectives collected from the "Explanatory

Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" represent 20% (540). She notes that 200 of them are positive, 270 are negative, and 70 are neutral adjectives[3].

Symbolic lexemes are found in texts of various contents. The essence of these lexemes, their role in illuminating the characteristic aspects of the world scene, and their value in providing a holistic picture of things and phenomena are expressed in the artistic text. When expressing the content of a work of art, increasing its effectiveness, revealing its idea, being able to express the national culture in words, and fully describing the spirit of the times and the psyche of the characters, every creator uses symbolic words. The writer chooses the appropriate words for each situation and uses them skillfully. Therefore, in the study of the characteristic cultural symbols in the Uzbek and Russian languages, in addition to explanatory dictionaries, artistic texts with connotative content were taken as a source[4].

In conclusion it should be highlighted that, studying intercultural relations, finding a suitable variant of lexemes in the process of translation, distinguishing real and lacunar units between languages is an important task of research in the direction of linguo-cultural studies. Symbolic words figuratively serve to increase the attractiveness and effectiveness of speech, illuminate the essence of events, and serve as an artistic image. Linguistic-cultural analysis of symbolic lexemes is important in elucidating the relationship between language and culture, collecting and expressing the national outlook, thinking, and values of symbolic lexemes, and in determining the national models of the linguistic landscape of the world.

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